

CAPABLE

CAnCer PAtients Better Life Experience

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Prototype of guideline-based decision component

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• Versions History

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1.0	20th May 2022	David Glasspool Alexandra Kogan Ella Barkan	
1.1	15th June 2022	David Glasspool Alexandra Kogan	First draft ready for internal review
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● Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.3 is a “demonstration” deliverable. Its purpose is to demonstrate the capabilities of the “guideline-based decision support” technology implemented in the project. This mainly involves two CAPABLE components, the Physician Decision Support System (PDSS) and the goal-based inference component GoCom that detects and mitigates drug-drug interactions as well as interactions between guideline recommendations. Two demonstrations are presented. The main demonstration shows how PDSS and GoCom work together to provide guideline-based decision support with goal-based detection and resolution of drug interactions. This is presented as a video of the PDSS and GoCom logs during a simulated run of a clinical scenario, with a voice-over and a walk-through in this document explaining each step of the demonstration. A secondary demonstration covers the modes of interaction that have been developed between the Predictive Model Component (PMC) and PDSS, allowing machine-learning based predictive analytics to be combined with guideline-based decision support and delivered to a physician at the point of care. This is an experimental feature which will not be used in the clinical pilot, thus its demonstration is more limited.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of this Report

This report accompanies the demonstration video available here:

https://capable-project.eu/d5-3_demo/

It provides a commentary to be read alongside the demonstration video but also provides technical context for the demonstration and adds reports on the operation of the key components PDSS (Physician Decision Support System) and GoCom (Goal-based Multimorbidity Controller), and the interaction between PDSS, GoCom and the Predictive Model Component (PMC) which together provide comprehensive and nuanced decision support to physician users of the CAPABLE system.

The primary demonstration shows how PDSS and GoCom work together to provide guideline-based decision support with goal-based detection and resolution of drug interactions. This is presented as a video of the PDSS and GoCom logs during a simulated run of a clinical scenario, with a voice-over and a walk-through in this document explaining each step of the demonstration.

A secondary demonstration presented only in this document and not included in the video covers the modes of interaction that have been developed between the Predictive Model Component and PDSS, allowing predictive analytics to be combined with guideline-based decision support and delivered to a physician at the point of care. This functionality is not being carried forward into the clinical pilot phase of the project (for safety reasons, as already explained previously) and so has not been developed as a primary part of PDSS.

1.2. Demonstration Scope

This deliverable will demonstrate the following:

- Operation of the PDSS component and its ability to provide guideline-based decision support to a physician within the CAPABLE infrastructure in a clinically realistic scenario;
- Ability to follow multiple CIG guidelines simultaneously for the same patient;
- Operation of the GoCom component and its interaction with PDSS to provide goal-based conflict checking and resolution on any prescribed medications.

These are considered the primary scope of this deliverable as a demonstration of guideline-based decision support. However a supplementary demonstration is provided of the techniques that have been developed to incorporate non-guideline decision support from the Predictive Model Component. At the moment, the outputs of the PMC are not approved for use in providing clinical guidance in any real patient-facing situation. Because of this, full API connectivity is not available within the PMC. With the purpose of demonstrating their potentiality in decision support, the supplementary demonstration is therefore presented as a set of static outputs and will show the following:

- Example decision support generated by running the PMC dynamically for a simulated patient in a highly simplified clinical scenario.

- Example decision support using generalised rules extracted from analysis of the PMC models, applied in a highly simplified clinical scenario.

These two types of demonstrated output are explained in Section 5.2.

1.3. Outline

The first part of this document (Sections 2 to 5) describes the operation of the CAPABLE system around the provision of decision support to physicians. These sections outline the components and interactions involved in this functionality, and then give a detailed report on the design and operation of the PDSS (Section 3) and GoCom (Section 4) components. Section 5.1 describes the interaction between GoCom and PDSS in more detail, and Section 5.2 does the same for the interaction between the PMC and PDSS. These sections show how goal-based reasoning and machine learning-based prediction have been merged with and incorporated into the CIG-based decision support provided by the deontics engine. (A detailed description of the functionality of the PMC is provided in deliverable D5.4.)

The second part of the document (Sections 6 and 7) presents the actual demonstrations. The main demonstration of guideline-based decision support with goal-based conflict detection and resolution is presented in the accompanying video and Section 6 provides a commentary to go with the video, explaining what is shown and how it relates to and demonstrates the functionality described in the first part of the document. Section 7 presents a supplementary demonstration of interaction between the PDSS and the PMC.

1.4. The PROforma CIG language

Several components within the CAPABLE decision support system make use of the Computer Interpretable Guideline (CIG) language PROforma [1]. This section introduces some aspects of the language that will be useful in later sections.

PROforma is a Task-based executable clinical decision support language. A small number of task types are used to represent data acquisition, the marshalling of information to support decision making by a human physician, and recommended actions. Medical logic is anchored to tasks which access data and formalise decisions, so even the simplest decision support application built with PROforma needs a basic task structure as a skeleton. Once formalized in the PROforma language a guideline can be executed (often referred to as “enactment”) by an execution engine. One such engine, produced by Deontics, is used in the CAPABLE project. This engine is hosted on a server and exposes a web API which can be used to upload PROforma CIGs and execute them using specific patient data.

In the PROforma language there are five types of task:

Enquiry: A task that requests values for data items. PROforma has a relatively simple data model in which data items that are required in order to implement the clinical logic of the guideline (generally patient data, e.g. *Age* or *Systolic Blood Pressure*) are defined in the CIG and are given values by the engine during enactment. The engine is responsible for retrieving a value for a data item when required by an enquiry task.

Action: A task that represents some action that should be performed in the world (e.g. sending a message to a physician). The engine provides an API that external processes can use to carry out Actions that require execution.

Decision Represents activities in which a choice is made between several different options. These are explored more fully below.

Plan: A container representing “compound” activities that are defined as a set of tasks.

Each *PROforma* Task has a number of properties that are used to implement the clinical logic of a guideline, for example a logical precondition (a logical expression which may be based for example on data values or the states of other Tasks) that must be satisfied before the Task can become active. It is also possible to define additional properties (called metaproperties) that may for example specify how to acquire a value for a data item, or how to carry out an action. These metaproperties might be used by an external process to pull data from a patient record system or send a message to a physician, for example.

1.4.1. The *PROforma* Argumentation Model

In *PROforma Decisions* are tasks in which a choice is made – either by the Engine or by a clinician user – between several different options. *PROforma* supports decision-making through a mechanism for evaluating arguments that may be either for or against a given option. The basic structure of an argument is shown in Figure 1. An argument is a rule that is triggered by some Data, and when it is triggered it makes some Claim. The argument has a Condition that defines exactly when the rule should be triggered, and a Weight which determines whether it argues for or against the claim, and how strongly. Finally the whole argument may be based on a piece of Evidence, such as a section of a guideline document:

Figure 1: *PROforma* Argument model

For example, a simple argument might be:

“Based on official guidelines, a patient presenting with persistent chest pain should be referred urgently for chest X-ray”

Here, the *Claim* is: “The patient should be referred urgently for chest X-ray”;

the relevant *Data* is the presenting symptoms of the patient;

the *Condition* is: “persistent chest pain”;

the *Weight* is: “For” or “+” (i.e. this is an argument in favour of the claim, not against it);

and the *Evidence* is a section of text in an official guideline document.

In *PROforma* arguments and claims are collected together within specialised tasks called *Decisions*. A *Decision* specifies a choice to be made between a set of alternative *Claims*, which are called the *Candidates* of the decision. Each *Candidate* has a number of *Arguments* attached, which can each increase or decrease the level of support for that candidate. A decision may use one of two alternative formats for support of candidates, either symbolic (the argument can be either for or against the candidate), or numeric (the support is defined using a numeric value; the argument has a weight assigned to it).

When a decision is enacted by a *PROforma* Engine, the condition and the support properties are used to determine the effect of each argument and in turn the aggregated effect for a given candidate. The aggregated support of all of a candidate's arguments is known as *netsupport*. A recommendation rule is then used to determine whether or not a particular candidate is recommended to the physician. This expression typically takes into account the candidate's *netsupport*.

(Note that physician end-users can choose non-recommended candidates if they wish. The *Decision* and its *Candidates* and *Arguments* are a way to marshal the evidence and present it to the physician in a way that makes it easy to see the various factors influencing a decision).

2. The CAPABLE Reasoning Framework

2.1. Overview of the component network providing guideline-based decision support

Figure 2: Simplified conceptual view of component network surrounding PDSS and GoCom. PMC is the Predictive Model Component, and KDOM is the Knowledge-Data Ontology Mapper. All blue components connect to DP (Data Platform) and CM (Case Manager), and the black arrows conceptually indicate interactions that take place via DP.

The Physician Decision Support System (PDSS) and GoCom components sit within a network of CAPABLE components as shown conceptually in Figure 2. This network of components has already been introduced in deliverable D5.2 Section 5.2, however it will be useful to recap the general arrangement and Figure 2 summarises the interactions between just the components involved in this document in a more focussed way.

The Data Platform (DP) and Case Manager (CM) components provide a central data and event management platform that is responsible for all interactions between CAPABLE components (all the components shown in blue in Figure 2). It is important to note that the arrows between blue components in Figure 2 indicate conceptual exchange of information and control messages between components, not physical connections. All these interactions are in fact mediated by the CP and DP, so CAPABLE components connect physically to CP and DP rather than to each other. (The orange arrows to the Deontics Computer Interpretable Guideline (CIG) server are different - they represent direct connection to the REST API on the server from three CAPABLE components which use the Deontics engine.)

Figure 2 shows the main interactions that are important for this deliverable; for clarity not every interaction path is shown.

PDSS provides guideline-based decision support to physician users of the CAPABLE system. It is responsible for sending any messages or recommendations indicated by the clinical guidelines to the physician user interface (Physician App) (via the Data Platform), and it uses the Deontics engine to execute *PROforma* guidelines for the various clinical conditions that are supported by CAPABLE. Adding support for a new clinical indication or revising the guidance for an existing one is done by adding to or editing the guidelines stored on the Deontics server; no changes to PDSS or any of the other components are required.

PDSS provides a means for the goal-based decision support provided by GoCom and the machine-learning-based decision support provided by the PMC to be directed to the physician. However in both cases this is not a simple matter of passing a message to the Physician App, the guidance for the physician is generated through a more complex interaction between PDSS and each of these components which will be discussed in this report.

3. Overview of Physician Decision Support Component

The PDSS uses the Deontics engine to execute CIGs for patients; it can deal with multiple patients simultaneously being assessed on multiple CIGs. PDSS interfaces between the CAPABLE component-oriented network architecture (see Figure 2) and FHIR data format, and the specialised CIG execution API and data model of the Deontics engine.

PDSS also implements an *assessment-based* workflow over the CIGs. This is a workflow that is based on repeated “assessments” of a patient, where assessments may happen at any time but are assumed to be brief - CIG execution is started, the CIG assesses the patient based on current clinical data and immediately returns any recommended actions that are indicated, and then execution stops. Each assessment starts afresh from the beginning of the CIG and is based solely on the current clinical data - no memory is retained in the Engine from one assessment to the next (i.e. the execution model is considered “stateless”). This stateless execution model is a general aim within the CAPABLE project as a means of reducing dependencies between components and increasing robustness, and it also allows more straightforward testing.

The diagram in Figure 3 shows the primary interactions that are orchestrated by the PDSS to implement this assessment-oriented workflow. Essentially, whenever new clinical data arrives for a patient, a single assessment is carried out on each available CIG using the patient’s clinical data. Some of these assessments may be very brief, where the CIG is immediately found not to be relevant to the patient, and some may involve more detailed processing.

Figure 3: PDSS functional cycle

Table 1 gives more detail about each interaction. Events 2 - 17 in the table show the operational cycle which is repeated each time a patient is assessed by PDSS, and this cycle will be clear in the demo of Section 6.

1	Initialisation phase carried out when PDSS starts up. PDSS registers rules with the CM to alert it to events of interest (new Observation, MedicationRequest or incoming Communication for PDSS). This causes CM to send an event to PDSS when any of these occur.
2	An event is generated by CM because new data (observation or medication) has been registered for a patient.
3, 4,5,6,7	PDSS determines whether any abstractions are needed from KDOM in order to run CIGs for the patient. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The available guidelines are checked for abstraction data items that are needed in order to run (3, 4). - Requests are sent to KDOM for all required abstractions (5).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KDOM responds by writing updated abstraction values to the DP (6) and confirming to PDSS that this has been done (7) <p>(NB currently all abstractions used in the CIG are requested; this may result in requesting abstractions that later turn out to be unnecessary if certain paths in the CIG can be skipped - for example if the patient does not have diarrhea, a diarrhea treatment CIG may finish execution very quickly after checking just that one fact, and not require any further data. A refinement to request abstractions progressively during CIG execution is planned as a possible upgrade.)</p>
8, 9, 10	Values are retrieved from DP for each data item that is required by the Deontics engine to run the currently available CIGs for the current patient (8, 9) and these are uploaded to the Deontics server (10)
11, 12	For each available CIG, the engine runs a single patient assessment against the current patient data (11), and returns an overall list of actions that are recommended (12)
13, 14, 15, 16, 17	<p>The requested actions are processed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Any actions requiring messages to be sent directly to the Physician App are carried out by writing Communication resources to DP (13) - Any actions requiring medications to be prescribed or withheld are carried out by writing appropriate draft MedicationRequest resources to DP (14) and sending a Communication to GoCom requesting an evaluation of any drug interactions they may incur (15) - GoCom returns a set of options for the physician to approve the recommended medications or choose between alternative options if interactions are found (16) - A Communication for the Physician App is written to DP to convey the options returned by GoCom (17).

Table 1. Detail of PDSS interactions

4. Overview of GoCom Component

GoCom (for Goal Comorbidities - Multimorbidity Controller) is a goal-oriented component that is responsible for detecting interactions and suggesting solutions for mitigating these interactions. The previous version of GoCom's methodology [2] was extended to include new types of interactions as well as means of integration with the CAPABLE system. The component is used as a service by the PDSS and the Virtual Coach in order to assess the viability of guideline-recommended pharmacological treatments and prevent adverse events that may be caused by interactions. The patient's diagnoses and treatments are conceptualized as goals that can be formed as goal-oriented hierarchical tree-graphs, where each of the patient's conditions is the root goal and has multiple children such as messages to the physician, pharmacological treatments and procedures. GoCom receives requests for consistency checking from PDSS and the Virtual Coach and constructs goal-trees from the received proposed medications combined with the patient's existing on-going medications retrieved from the Data Platform.

In order to check for consistency of guideline medication recommendations, GoCom compares the codes of pairs of recommendations. If the code of one recommendation is the same as another or is subsumed by the drug-class, the statuses of the recommendations are examined. An inconsistency between guideline recommendations happens when two guidelines have different recommendation statuses for the same drug. For example - one guideline recommends a drug with an "active" status and another guideline recommends to suspend or stop that same drug. Drug-drug interactions are detected by using the RxNav API. For each pair of medications, their RxNorm codes are extracted and a search is performed in the RxNav interactions database. If an interaction between the two codes exists, the explanation for it is added to the explanation of the goal that is later displayed to the user.

When interactions are detected, GoCom performs a search in the guideline that recommended the inconsistent goal for replacements of each interacting treatment. If a replacement is found, it will be suggested instead of the originally recommended treatment as an alternative. If no replacement was found, GoCom will create an alternative recommendation without the interacting treatment. Finally, GoCom attaches an explanation to all treatments that are either retrieved from the guideline or auto-generated according to the inconsistency that occurred. This results in multiple disjoint option-sets for the patient's inconsistent goals. Each option-set is a variation of the conflicted goals and their suggested treatments that can be achieved concurrently without causing interactions. The patient's consistent goals that are not part of an interaction are also constructed in a similar way but are displayed to the physician user as recommended by the guideline, with no alternatives.

Example case study 1 - Drug Drug Interaction

A patient that has been treated with the targeted therapy drug Sunitinib, is prescribed the anti-diarrhoea drug Loperamide by the diarrhoea guideline to be used as needed due to cancer therapy toxicity. The nausea guideline recommends treating the patient with

Ondansetron, a drug for preventing nausea and vomiting that may occur due to cancer therapy toxicity. PDSS sends both recommendations to GoCom. The recommendations are placed in a tree structure and GoCom checks them for consistency. Indeed, a drug-drug interaction is found between Loperamide and Ondansetron. Since no alternatives are suggested by the guidelines, GoCom outputs the two option-sets that can be seen in Figure 4. For complete JSON and explanations please see Annex 2. The option-sets are stored in the Data Platform and the PDSS or Virtual Coach component that sent the interaction checking request (in this case the PDSS) are informed via communication.

Goal	Option-set 1	Option-set 2
Treatment of Diarrhea	Prescribe Loperamide Loperamide can be started at an initial dose of 4mg followed by 2mg every 2–4 hours or after every unformed stool [II, B]...	Reject Loperamide recommendation An interaction has been found between Loperamide and Ondansetron: The metabolism of Ondansetron...
Treatment of Nausea	Reject Ondansetron recommendation An interaction has been found between Loperamide and Ondansetron: The metabolism of can be decreased when combined with Loperamide...	Prescribe Ondansetron Recommended doses of serotonin (5-HT) ₃ receptor antagonists: Ondansetron IV 8 mg or 0.15 mg/kg, Ondansetron Oral 16 mga...

Figure 4: An example output of option-sets for an interaction between Loperamide and Ondansetron.

Example case study 2 - No interactions

The patient from case 1 was prescribed Loperamide as needed for diarrhoea due to cancer therapy toxicity (option-set 1 in Figure 4). When the patient starts experiencing diarrhoea and reports it through the CAPABLE system, the guideline recommends Racecadotril that is sent by the PDSS to GoCom for interaction checking. The guideline also recommends to send messages to the physician regarding the previously prescribed Loperamide and management of uncomplicated diarrhea that are not forwarded to GoCom since they are not pharmacological interventions. GoCom does not find any interactions with Racecadotril and produces one single option-set with the recommendation to prescribe the medication. The option-set is stored in the Data Platform and a communication is sent to the PDSS.

5. Overview of integration of reasoning models

5.1. GoCom - PDSS interaction

The CIGs that are modeled in PROforma reflect GoCom's goal-oriented view and have a main root plan which is used as the root goal of each goal-tree of the patient. The root plan of each guideline has the following plans:

- Data plan - contains all the inquiries with the data items to be used for running the guideline
- Prevention plan - contains recommendations for preventing the condition if the patient is at risk of experiencing the condition. An example would be a recommendation to prescribe Loperamide to take it as needed, to a patient that is on immunotherapy, even though the patient has not reported any occurrence of diarrhea yet.
- Diagnosis plan - has a decision with two possible candidates that determine whether the side effect is related to the cancer treatment or not. The data items that help make that decision can come from the patient record (for example - if a patient is taking immunotherapy drugs then it is implied that the side effect could be due to immunotherapy toxicity), additionally, the physician may explicitly state whether the symptom is related to cancer therapy toxicity or not.
- Treatment plan - consists of the different decisions and treatments that result from them (both messages to the physician and pharmacological interventions).
- Monitoring plan - contains monitoring recommendations for the patient's condition.

Each action in the guideline has a number of metaproperties that help other components (including GoCom) reason over the recommendations:

- Ontology coding - provides the code for pharmacological treatments (medications) and procedures with the appropriate terminology (e.g., RxNorm, SNOMED-CT).
- Intervention type - specifies the intervention type of the action task that is suggested by the guideline. For messages to the physician the intervention type is "message" and for proposed pharmacological treatments (medications) the intervention type is "medication-proposal".
- Status - one of the *statuses* for a Medication Request FHIR resource (e.g., active, canceled).
- Intent - one of the *intents* for a Medication Request FHIR resource. When the Medication Request resource is generated by the PDSS, the status is always "proposal". When generated by the Physician App, the status is "order". That helps the components identify medication requests that were proposed by the system and ones that were prescribed by the physician.
- Explanation location - the location of the evidence and grade of evidence from the guideline that is mapped to that specific action during the modeling phase. The evidence could be located in the "procedure" part of the action-task or in the candidate of the decision that precedes the action and correlates with the action itself. For example, a treatment decision could contain several candidates: *candidate_a*, *candidate_b* and *candidate_tc*. If *candidate_a* is selected, then the corresponding *action_a* would be then suggested by the guideline. The explanation for *action_a*

would reside in the arguments of *candidate_a* where we would see the direct mapping to the text in the clinical guideline document.

- Response needed - indicates whether a response by a physician is needed regarding that particular action. Messages to the physician would usually not need a response whereas pharmacological treatments always require the physician to provide some feedback (either prescribe the medication or decline the proposed treatment).
- Dosage instruction - the dosage instruction of a pharmacological treatment in JSON format.
- Dispense request - the dispense request of a pharmacological treatment in JSON format.
- Decision - the name of the decision that contains the corresponding candidate to indicate the recommendation of the action-task.
- Gate - the relationship between the different actions that have scheduling constraints with a specific decision. The gate can be “OR” which means that one or more actions that are recommended according to a specific decision, need to be prescribed by the physician to adhere to the recommendation in the guideline. For an “AND” gate, all the recommended tasks need to be completed for adherence to guideline recommendations. Subsequently for a “XOR”, only one of the recommended tasks should be completed but not the others. The use of gates captures relevant knowledge from the guideline thus allowing to display all valid options to the physician user and facilitating operations by the Physician App.

The metaproperties described above allow GoCom to process the tasks recommended by the guideline and create option-sets that match the objectives of the guideline, while taking into account possible interactions that might require mitigation.

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5.2. Predictive Model Component - PDSS interaction

The interaction between the Predictive Model Component (PMC) and PDSS is based around the *PROforma* Argumentation Model introduced in Section 1.4. This section shows how this argumentation model can be used to introduce additional decision support guidance alongside that based on formal guideline documents. This has allowed us to develop two routes by which decision support guidance can be generated by the PMC.

5.2.1. Predictive model argumentation routes

To add decision support derived from a predictive model to that provided by pre-compiled CIG guidelines, using the Argumentation model outlined above, we can add new Arguments for existing Candidates within existing Decisions. A feature of the argumentation model that makes this tractable is that arguments can easily be designed to be *purely additive* - that is, adding a new argument to an existing candidate need not interfere with or interact in any way with existing arguments; each argument constitutes a separate line of reasoning for or against the candidate, and it is the clinical end user who takes an overall view of the weight of evidence for each candidate.

Another feature of the *PROforma* argumentation framework that allows us to use arguments generated from predictive models is that arguments may often be indicative rather than conclusive. The physician is not being told which is the “correct” choice, but is presented with a range of different pieces of relevant information that they can use to *inform* their choice. In this context arguments generated from a predictive model, which are not clinically validated and may not be based on real clinical factors, can be presented as additional information only, so that they may be taken into account within the mix of factors affecting a decision only if desired.

We have developed two routes by which new Arguments can be generated from the PMC. Both will be demonstrated below (Section 7). (NB The Deontics Engine has an API that allows arguments to be dynamically added to enactments, so it is possible to generate arguments and introduce them into a CIG while it is running; however for the present demonstrations a simpler approach is being used where arguments are generated and added to the CIG immediately before running it.)

Route I

This can be considered a *local* or *patient-specific* route. Arguments are generated that are completely specific to a particular patient being treated. This is done by running the predictive model on the specific clinical data for the patient, and obtaining patient-specific predictions for key outcome measures which can be used as the basis for an argument for or against an existing decision candidate. Generally this can be done on the basis of differences in the predicted outcome value when compared across different scenarios (corresponding to different decision candidates). In practice this corresponds to a form of “what-if” analysis where the PMC makes a set of predictions based on different “scenarios” that correspond to the different candidates - for example if the candidates represent different treatment options, the PMC must generate predicted outputs for each, each one based on the patient’s data plus the assumption of one or other of the treatment options. This may be achieved in the PMC using a single model trained on all of the treatments (so that the specific treatment being

assumed is one of the input features of the model), or using a set of models each trained using a different treatment.

For example, an argument might be constructed in favour of a treatment option, on the basis that the PMC predicts a lower probability of some undesired side effect when compared with other available options.

Here, the interesting difference in predicted outcome is the different predicted probability of the side effect when the predictive model is fed two scenarios, both based on the same patient data and with all other input factors held the same apart from the treatment option chosen.

At present, we consider only *symbolic* arguments (that is, arguments which have a polarity - for or against a candidate - but no relative magnitude, see Section 1.4). However with the addition of some means to rank arguments by strength or force it would be possible to implement a measure of relative weight by switching to *numeric* arguments. This is not attempted at present but mention will be made below of the possibility of using patient preferences to achieve this.

Arguments generated via this route are specific to a particular patient in a particular clinical situation, and therefore need to be automatically generated by the PMC during CIG execution. They are unusual in that they do not need to be evaluated by the PROforma execution engine (they are effectively evaluated by the PMC when they are generated), so they do not have a Condition expression that needs to be evaluated by the Engine (their Condition is “true()”).

In order to do this automatic generation of arguments two pieces of meta-information are needed:

1. It is necessary to map certain decision candidates in a CIG to input features in the predictive model. E.g. a decision candidate “Combined targetted and immunological therapy” in a cancer treatment decision might map to a corresponding model input feature representing this type of combined therapy. In some cases these mappings may not be simple, so it needs to be possible to map a single PROforma Candidate to an extended fragment of a model input feature vector.
2. It is necessary to provide an indication of at least the polarity of the subjective benefit or harm to the patient of model outcome measures. For example an outcome measure predicting higher toxicity levels for one set of input features compared with another is subjectively bad for the patient, and should be interpreted as an argument against any input features that tend to increase it, whereas a prediction of comparatively longer disease-free survival is subjectively good and should count as an argument in favour of features that increase it.

An additional piece of information that may be useful is a ranking of the subjective importance of different outcome measures. This can be used to order recommendations to the physician, in order to provide a more useful summary. This may rely on patient personal preferences. For example a patient may rank nausea as a less important harm than reduced survival, so any option that increased the likelihood of survival at the cost of increased probability of nausea would be highly ranked. In some situations a different patient might make a different ranking. These preferences could in principle be accommodated via numeric weights on PROforma arguments.

We have implemented code to automatically generate arguments via Route I which we demonstrate in Section 7.

Route II

This can be considered a *global* or *population-based* route. Arguments are generated by analysing the predictive model to find input features that correlate strongly with outputs that are particularly desired or unwanted. These regularities, if found, can be represented via the arguments as new explicit rules that can then be presented to clinicians (clearly identified as originating from predictive models) to be assessed for their potential clinical validity alongside official CIG guidance. Generally, predicted output values can be used in this way only if there are comparative values available, e.g average or expected values, so that it is possible to make claims that e.g. “input feature X is correlated in the model with higher than average predicted value of output feature Y”.

This route generates new arguments from the predictive model but does not do so in a patient-specific way. Argument generation can be done off-line and arguments combined with conventional CIG arguments before the system is used.

We have implemented a technique to generate arguments offline in this way, and we show the results in Section 7. Our approach uses SHAP analysis of a pair of predictive models trained on scenarios that differ in the value of the input feature of interest (corresponding to a pair of PROforma Candidates, e.g. “combined therapy” and “monotherapy”).

To illustrate the approach, Figure 5 shows a pair of SHAP plots for models based on combined or mono-therapy, showing the relative influence of input features on the predicted value of Toxicity.

Toxicity (for 1st line treatment, updated features)

Figure 5: SHAP plots for toxicity in models based on mono or combined therapy for Melanoma

The Route II technique that we have implemented looks for features that appear high in one of the plots but low in the other (i.e. features that have an evident impact on the output in one scenario but not the other). This aims to identify relatively straightforward cases where

features are important for one candidate but not another, and are thus a good potential basis for a generalised rule. Clearly there are other patterns we could look for in the differential influence of features between plots, but we have chosen this simple case as a starting point.

For example in Figure 5 the feature “risk factors” appears high on the right-hand side (the combined treatment case) but not on the left (the monotherapy case). This feature is a numerical score that combines a number of risk factors:

- bone mets
- brain mets
- liver mets,
- Who > 0,
- increased_S100,
- increased_LDH

The red tail of the plot for risk factors on the right-hand plot indicates that high values here are often correlated with lower toxicity levels in combined therapy patients (it is important to note that this is simply a correlation that emerges from the model; we do not aim to explore the causal factors or clinical foundation for the relationship, we simply note that it may be a useful piece of information for a physician making a judgement on likelihood of toxicity for a patient with a high risk factor score). The presence of any risk factors (ie a “risk factors” score > 0) is thus a potential condition that could be used for an argument *in favour* of combined therapy, on the basis that these risk factors tend to correlate with a lower toxicity response than usual with combined therapy.

Again, similar meta-data about the mapping of model input features to PROforma candidates, and the subjective direction and possibly ranking of output measures are required as for the Route I case in order to generate concrete arguments from this analysis.

This route does not yield patient-specific arguments like Route I, but instead it has the potential to generate interesting general insights that could, if clinically validated, lead to updating of conventional guideline recommendations with new arguments from predictive models.

6. Demonstration 1 (Guideline-based and goal-based Decision Support)

6.1. Demonstration 1 scope

This is the primary demonstration of PDSS and GoCom operation, showing how guideline-based and goal-based decision support are generated and combined. The functionality demonstrated here will be available for clinical piloting in the pilot studies.

The PDSS demo video can be summarized as follows:

1. The video shows the log output of the PDSS component live as it responds to patient data representing the steps in the clinical scenario.
2. The scenario is controlled by the CAPABLE Simulator system, implemented by the UNIPV team.
3. For this demonstration, the simulator runs through the two steps in the scenario. For each step, it writes FHIR resources to the Data Platform simulating the actual patient data that would appear there in the scenario.
4. The other CAPABLE components, GoCom, KDOM and Virtual Coach, are also connected into the system and running live, and some activity in the PDSS log reflects their responses to the scenario. Messages are passed between the components via Communication resources in the Data Platform.

The video demonstrates the following features of PDSS and GoCom (timestamps in parentheses indicate locations in the log of Annex 1 where these features can be seen in the demo; corresponding offsets in the video are given in Table 2):

1. PDSS is able to register rules with CM to request that it is informed of new patient data (MedicationRequests and Observations) and incoming Communications addressed to it appearing in the Data Platform. (14:42:42)
2. PDSS is able to use arbitrary *PROforma* CIGs stored on the Deontics engine server to execute clinical guidelines (14:42:42). It uses the Deontics runtime engine API (DRE-API) to upload patient data, run execution cycles for each guideline and retrieve recommended actions from the engine.
3. PDSS responds to new patient data (14:44:57) by requesting any abstractions needed by the current CIGs from KDOM (14:44:58), and then running each of the CIGs for the patient in question (14:45:14, 14:45:15).
4. PDSS can execute multiple guidelines simultaneously for the same patient (14:45:14, 14:45:15).
5. PDSS interacts with GoCom to check for interactions between medications recommended by guidelines. This can cover several possible cases:
 - a. Interactions between a recommended medication and any other medication that the patient is already receiving;
 - b. Interactions between two medications recommended by the same guideline (this should be unusual, CIGs are generally designed to avoid internal interactions of this sort and this might be considered a type of error detection);

- c. Interactions between medications recommended by two independent guidelines.

The third of these cases is interesting because this allows a patient to be cared for according to multiple guidelines simultaneously while maintaining safety, without the guidelines having to be specifically designed with awareness of the others they will be used alongside. This is the case demonstrated here (14:45:21).

- 6. PDSS is able to carry out two different types of action in response to *PROforma* Action tasks becoming active in a CIG:
 - a. Medication actions: These resolve into FHIR MedicationRequest resources that are written to the Data Platform (14:45:17). RXNORM ontology coding is used for drug type, and Metaproperties on the *PROforma* Action define the dosage and dispensing instructions. GoCom is always invoked to check these for interactions with existing medications or others recommended at the same time.
 - b. Message actions: These resolve into text messages to be displayed to the Physician via the CAPABLE Physician App. They are sent as Communication resources written to the Data Platform and addressed to the Physician App. (14:46:49)

6.2. Demonstration 1 scenario

The clinical scenario for the demonstration is adapted from a scenario created by the CAPABLE WP3 clinical guideline team for internal testing of the clinical pilot system. It concerns a patient receiving combined targeted and immunological treatment for melanoma, and focuses on clinical guidance for managing side effects of the primary cancer treatment.

The scenario as adapted for this demonstration is not intended to be fully clinically realistic. Its primary purpose is to exercise the PDSS and GoCom components and demonstrate their operation and interaction. For this purpose a short fragment of a clinical scenario with only two main steps has been chosen.

Demo Scenario

Step 1: Enrollment

The Physician, through the Physician App, enrolls a new patient Maria Rossi.

Since the patient is under Sunitinib treatment (44% incidence of diarrhea), the diarrhea guideline recommends an anti-diarrhea medication (Loperamide) to be taken as needed.

The nausea guideline also reacts to the fact that the patient is being given Sunitinib. It recommends an anti-nausea medication, Ondansetron.

There is a potential interaction between Loperamide and Ondansetron. The CAPABLE system picks this up and suggests ways in which it could be avoided. The recommendation is passed to the Physician via the Physician App.

The physician accepts the recommendation to prescribe Loperamide.

Step 2: Symptoms

Patient Maria Rossi starts to experience the symptom of diarrhea. Through the Patient App she inserts the symptom diarrhea grade 1.

Because the patient reports diarrhea, The guideline checks whether there is Complicated Diarrhea or Persistent Diarrhea. Neither is the case. The guideline therefore makes the following recommendations to the physician:

Uncomplicated diarrhea initial management advice message (a text message sent to the Physician App covering simple steps the patient can take to mitigate mild diarrhea);

Loperamide advice message (a text message sent to the Physician App: The patient has already been prescribed Loperamide to be taken as needed; this is to indicate that now would be a good time for the patient to take it.)

Racecadotril: A recommended medication prescription.

These recommendations are passed to the Physician via the Physician App. The physician makes the final decision about how to manage the patient.

6.3. Demonstration 1 clinical guideline

For the main demo, two clinical guidelines (CIGs) are used, the ESMO diarrhea guideline [3], and a nausea guideline which has been modeled purposely for this demo. The purpose of this second guideline is to demonstrate the ability of PDSS to manage a patient according to two different guidelines simultaneously, and to demonstrate the detection and management of interactions between drug treatments by GoCom.

The PROforma executable CIG code for these guidelines is available at the following URLs:

Diarrhea guideline:

https://capable-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/tech_diarrhea_physicians_revised.pf

Nausea guideline:

https://capable-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/tech_nausea_test.pf

6.4. Demonstration 1 video walkthrough

Table 2 provides a walkthrough of the demo video (and Annex 1 log) showing what exactly is happening at each step.

Video timestamp	Log timestamp (Annex 1)	Notes
0:30	14:42:41	<p>PDSS initialises and checks its connections to the CAPABLE Case Manager (CM) and Data Platform (DP) and to the Deontics CIG execution engine.</p> <p>It registers rules with the CM to be alerted to new Observations, MedicationRequests or Communications addressed to itself.</p> <p>Two CIGs are available on the Deontics engine server, for nausea and diarrhea.</p>
0:50	14:44:57	<p>Step 1 of the scenario starts. CM notifies the PDSS that a new MedicationRequest has been written to the Data Platform, for the medication Sunitinab for the demo scenario patient Maria Rossi (referred to as patient paz-0 by the CAPABLE Simulator in this case).</p>
1:00	14:44:58	<p>PDSS responds to changed patient data by preparing to execute each of its available CIGs for the patient.</p> <p>Its first step is to check if any of the data items required by these CIGs are KDOM abstractions. Some are, so PDSS sends requests for these abstractions to KDOM.</p>
1:10	14:45:14	<p>KDOM responds by updating the values of the requested abstractions for this patient in the DP, and PDSS then proceeds to execute each of its CIGs for the patient.</p>
1:14	14:45:17	<p>Two actions are activated within these CIGs. One is a medication recommendation for the anti-nausea drug Ondansetron from the nausea guideline, and the other is the drug Loperamide from the diarrhea guideline.</p> <p>Draft medication requests for each of these are sent to DP, and a message is sent to GoCom requesting that these be checked for possible drug interactions.</p>
1:35	14:45:21	<p>GoCom responds with a message that an interaction has been found between Ondansetron and Loperamide.</p> <p>It suggests two strategies to avoid this, either withholding Ondansetron or Loperamide.</p> <p>PDSS sends a message to the CAPABLE Physician App referencing this set of medication options and explanations</p>

		from GoCom. This will be formatted and displayed to the physician who can make a decision about what to actually prescribe.
2:20	14:46:29	Step 2 of the scenario starts. CM notifies the PDSS that a new Observation has been written to the Data Platform, indicating that the demo patient has reported grade 1 diarrhea.
2:38	14:46:30	Up-to-date values for all required abstractions are again requested from KDOM, as the changed patient data may affect their values.
2:46	14:46:46	KDOM responds by writing updated values to DP and sending messages to PDSS to let it know this has happened.
2:49	14:46:47	PDSS executes each of its CIGs for the demo patient. Three actions are activated, all in the diarrhea guideline:
3:00	14:46:49	A direct message for the Clinician with basic recommendations for uncomplicated diarrhea; this will be sent direct to the Physician App for display to the physician;
3:00	14:46:50	A recommendation for the drug Racecadotril; a draft MedicationRequest is written to DP;
3:00	14:46:50	A direct message for the Clinician with advice that the previous prescription of Loperamide “as needed” should be taken up by the patient at this point.
3:20	14:46:50	A message is sent to GoCom requesting a check of Racecadotril for possible interactions with any other drug the patient is receiving.
3:26	14:47:02	GoCom responds that no interaction is found; PDSS passes a message on to the Physician App with the recommendation and a reference to the Racecadotril draft medication request.

Table 2: Walkthrough of the demo video (and Annex 1 log)

7. Supplementary Demonstration (Predictive Model based decision support)

7.1. Supplementary Demonstration scope

This supplementary demonstration covers integration of PMC output into the guideline-based decision support system.

This functionality is demonstrated via a limited functional prototype that shows a practical implementation of the techniques outlined in Section 5.2. The demonstration uses a more limited and less clinically realistic scenario in order to focus directly on the core functionality.

The demonstration will cover the following functionality:

- Generation of arguments based on personalised predictive model output (Route I)
- Generation of arguments based on generalised population-level predictive model SHAP analysis (Route II)
- Combination of arguments generated by Routes I and II with conventional CIG arguments.

Unlike the main demonstration of Section 6 this functionality will be demonstrated only by showing the output in this document (as screen captures of a static decision support system interface), there is no associated video as the demonstration is much more limited in scope.

7.2. Supplementary Demonstration scenario

Advanced melanoma that cannot be surgically treated (unresectable metastatic melanoma) may be treated using a range of therapies including more recently introduced types of immunotherapy. Two types of immunotherapy regime, PD-1/PD-L1 and anti-CTLA-4 immune-checkpoint inhibitors, are available, and are recommended by various clinical guidelines (e.g. [3] and [4]) either in a monotherapy regime with a PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitor alone, or a combined therapy regime with both PD-1/PD-L1 and anti-CTLA-4 inhibitors. The clinical evidence regarding which is more beneficial is still weak at present [4] so published guidelines such as [3, 4] offer no advice about whether to use mono or combined therapy, leaving the decision to the physician. There is preliminary evidence that the combined regime is more effective but with higher probability of toxicity [5]. The CAPABLE PMC can provide predictive output to support this decision (although it is not trained on a large enough dataset to be clinically reliable).

The following demonstration assumes a scenario in which a physician is managing a patient with advanced unresectable metastatic melanoma and is evaluating the choice between mono or combined immunotherapy regimes. The CAPABLE decision support system provides the available standard advice derived from the ESMO guideline (which supports either option but does not advise which would be better), along with arguments for and against each option created via Route I and Route II of Section 5.2.

7.3. Supplementary Demonstration clinical guideline

For this demonstration, a simple clinical guideline was created based on a fragment of the ESMO Melanoma guideline [3] surrounding the decision between mono or combined immunotherapy as described in the scenario above. The guideline comprises a single Decision with two Candidates (mono or combined therapy), and a single Argument for each of the Candidates based on the ESMO advice that either option is acceptable.

7.4. Supplementary Demonstration output

Figures 6 and 7 below show output generated from the standard Deontics test user interface with the PROforma engine running the demonstration guideline and introducing dynamically generated Route I arguments and offline-generated Route II arguments.

Figure 6: Example decision support display for the mono vs combined therapy decision, combining guideline recommendations, patient-specific predictions and arguments extracted from SHAP plots
 (This patient has metastatic melanoma and “risk factors” = true)

Supporting or opposing evidence

-

PD-1 blockade or PD-1 and ipilimumab are now a standard of care for all patients, regardless of their BRAF status, in the first-line setting [1,A]

Evidence sources: ESMO Melanoma guideline page 14
-

For this patient, the predictive model suggests the following:

 - Predicted probability of grade 2-4 toxicity in monotherapy: 0.65 (average is 0.5)
 - Predicted probability of grade 2-4 toxicity in in combined therapy: 0.70 (average is 0.6)
-

For this patient, the predictive model suggests the following:

 - Predicted 2-year survival probability in monotherapy: 0.6 (average is 0.5)
 - Predicted 2-year survival probability in combined therapy: 0.70 (average is 0.6)
-

Presence of risk factors is correlated with lower predicted probability of toxicity in the combined therapy regime but is not significantly correlated with toxicity in the monotherapy regime.

Figure 7: Just the first section from the previous slide, with arguments fully expanded in the display to show more detail.

8. Glossary

CIG	Computer Interpretable Guideline
CM	Case Manager
DP	Data Platform
PDSS	Physician Decision Support System
GoCom	Goal Comorbidities (Multimorbidity Controller)
KDOM	Knowledge-Data Ontological Mapper
PMC	Predictive Model Component

9. References

- [1] David Sutton, John Fox. The Syntax and Semantics of the PROforma Guideline Modeling Language. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, Volume 10, Issue 5, September 2003, Pages 433–443
- [2] Alexandra Kogan, Mor Peleg, Samson W. Tu, Raviv Allon, Natanel Khaitov, Irit Hochberg. Towards a goal-oriented methodology for clinical-guideline-based management recommendations for patients with multimorbidity: GoCom and its preliminary evaluation. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics* 2020; 112.
- [3] Cutaneous melanoma: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. O. Michielin, A. C. J. van Akkooi, P. A. Ascierto, R. Dummer & U. Keilholz. *Annals of Oncology* 2019; 30: 1884–1901.
- [4] Systemic Therapy for Melanoma: ASCO Guideline. Rahul Seth, Hans Messersmith, Varinder Kaur, John M. Kirkwood, Ragini Kudchadkar, Jennifer Leigh McQuade, Anthony Provenzano, Umang Swami, et. al. *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 2020; 38:33, 3947-3970
- [5] Chae YK, Arya A, Iams W, et al. Current landscape and future of dual anti-CTLA4 and PD-1/PD-L1 blockade immunotherapy in cancer; lessons learned from clinical trials with melanoma and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) *Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer* 2018; 6:39. doi: 10.1186/s40425-018-0349-3

10. Annexes

10.1. Annex 1: PDSS demonstration log

This is the log captured from PDSS during the demonstration shown in the video.

```

===== Physician DSS Component =====
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] * DRE_SERVER_URL: https://cap-dev.deontics.com/dwe/a/Scenario_diarrhea/
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] * DATA_HOST: 34.252.224.79
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] * DATA_PORT: 8443
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] * DATA_ENDPOINT: dataplatform/fhir
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] * CM_HOST: 34.252.224.79
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] * CM_PORT: 8444
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] Initialising Physician DSS component version 0.3-6
Jun 14 2022 14:42:41 [INFO ] Deontics engine connection ok
Jun 14 2022 14:42:42 [INFO ] Found all 2 configured clinical pathways on DRE server:
Jun 14 2022 14:42:42 [INFO ]   tech_nausea_test
Jun 14 2022 14:42:42 [INFO ]   Diarrhea_Physicians_tech_revised
Jun 14 2022 14:42:42 [INFO ] Case Manager connection ok
Jun 14 2022 14:42:42 [INFO ] Successfully created CM event rules
Jun 14 2022 14:42:42 [INFO ] Finished initialisation with no errors
Jun 14 2022 14:44:57 [INFO ] ** New MedicationRequest for patient paz_0, MedicationRequest/3870 sunitinib
Jun 14 2022 14:44:58 [INFO ] Requesting updated abstractions for patient paz_0
Jun 14 2022 14:45:14 [INFO ] KDOM request completed for patient paz_0
Jun 14 2022 14:45:14 [INFO ] Running assessment for patient paz_0 on pathway tech_nausea_test
Jun 14 2022 14:45:15 [INFO ] Running assessment for patient paz_0 on pathway
Diarrhea_Physicians_tech_revised
Jun 14 2022 14:45:17 [INFO ] Execute Medication action for patient 529, med ondansetron for Action
tech_nausea_test_recommend_anti_nausea
Jun 14 2022 14:45:17 [INFO ] Execute Medication action for patient 529, med loperamide for Action
Diarrhea_Physicians_tech_revised_Loperamide_as_needed
Jun 14 2022 14:45:17 [INFO ] Sending a message to GoCom
Jun 14 2022 14:45:17 [INFO ] Sent communication Communication/12386
Jun 14 2022 14:45:21 [INFO ] New Option Set for patient paz_0 with type: medication-proposal and goal
ref: Goal/267
Interaction: true
An interaction has been found between recommend_anti_nausea and Loperamide_as_needed: The metabolism of
Ondansetron can be decreased when combined with Loperamide.
. This option suggests to omit recommend_anti_nausea and continue with Loperamide_as_needed
- MedicationRequest/3871
null
- MedicationRequest/3872
An interaction has been found between recommend_anti_nausea and Loperamide_as_needed: The metabolism of
Ondansetron can be decreased when combined with Loperamide.
. This option suggests to omit Loperamide_as_needed and continue with recommend_anti_nausea
- MedicationRequest/3872
null
- MedicationRequest/3871
Interaction: false
Jun 14 2022 14:45:21 [INFO ] Sending goal reference Goal/267 to Physician GUI
Jun 14 2022 14:45:21 [INFO ] Sent communication Communication/12389
Jun 14 2022 14:46:29 [INFO ] ** New Observation for patient paz_0, Observation/7779 Diarrhea
Jun 14 2022 14:46:30 [INFO ] Requesting updated abstractions for patient paz_0
Jun 14 2022 14:46:46 [INFO ] KDOM request completed for patient paz_0
Jun 14 2022 14:46:47 [INFO ] Running assessment for patient paz_0 on pathway tech_nausea_test
Jun 14 2022 14:46:48 [INFO ] Running assessment for patient paz_0 on pathway
Diarrhea_Physicians_tech_revised
Jun 14 2022 14:46:49 [INFO ] Execute Communication action for patient 530, destination: CPB:GUIS,
content: The following recommendations, suitably rephrased, have been sent to the patient by the CAPABLE
system: Initial management of mild to moderate diarrhoea should include dietary modifications (e.g.
eliminating all lactose-containing products and high-osmolar dietary supplements) and the patient should be
  
```

```
instructed to record the number of stools and report symptoms of life-threatening sequelae (e.g. fever or dizziness on standing). Special attention should be given to patients who are incontinent of stool due to the risk of pressure ulcer formation. Skin barriers should be used to prevent skin irritation caused by faecal material. Spices and beverages such as coffee and alcohol should be avoided and reduction of insoluble fibre intake may also be useful [V, C]. Diluted fruit juices and flavoured soft drinks along with saltine crackers and broths or soups may meet the fluid and salt needs in patients with mild illness.
Jun 14 2022 14:46:49 [INFO ] Sent communication Communication/12425
Jun 14 2022 14:46:50 [INFO ] Execute Medication action for patient 530, med racecadotril for Action Diarrhea_Physicians_tech_revised_Racecadotril
Jun 14 2022 14:46:50 [INFO ] Execute Communication action for patient 530, destination: CPB:GUIS, content: Loperamide should have been prescribed at the enrollment as a drug to be taken "as needed". If that prescription has been done, the patient has already received the recommendation to take loperamide. If not, consider that: Loperamide can be started at an initial dose of 4mg followed by 2mg every 2-4 hours or after every unformed stool [II, B]. The maximum daily dose of loperamide is 16 mg. One should pay attention to the risk of causing paralytic ileus and, even if rare, these patients need to be monitored while using high-dose loperamide. After 48 hours, in case of absence of efficacy of loperamide, administration of other drugs should be considered.
Jun 14 2022 14:46:50 [INFO ] Sent communication Communication/12427
Jun 14 2022 14:46:50 [INFO ] Sending a message to GoCom
Jun 14 2022 14:46:50 [INFO ] Sent communication Communication/12428
Jun 14 2022 14:46:52 [INFO ] ** New MedicationRequest for patient paz_0, MedicationRequest/3878 loperamide
Jun 14 2022 14:46:52 [INFO ] Requesting updated abstractions for patient paz_0
Jun 14 2022 14:47:02 [INFO ] New Option Set for patient paz_0 with type: medication-proposal and goal ref: Goal/268
Interaction: false
null
- MedicationRequest/3879
Jun 14 2022 14:47:02 [INFO ] Sending goal reference Goal/268 to Physician GUI
Jun 14 2022 14:47:02 [INFO ] Sent communication Communication/12448
```

10.2. Annex 2: GoCom option-sets output in JSON format

```

1  [
2  {
3    "interaction": "true",
4    "setOfOptionSets": [
5      {
6        "optionSet": [
7          {
8            "treatment": [
9              {
10             "requestReference": "MedicationRequest/4380"
11           }
12         ],
13         "explanation": "An interaction has been found between Loperamide and
14           Ondansetron: The metabolism of Ondansetron can be decreased when combined
15           with Loperamide. This option suggests to omit Loperamide and continue with
16           Ondansetron"
17       },
18       {
19         "treatment": [
20           {
21             "requestReference": "MedicationRequest/4398"
22           }
23         ],
24         "explanation": "Recommended doses of serotonin (5-HT)3 receptor antagonists:
25           Ondansetron IV 8 mg or 0.15 mg/kg, Ondansetron Oral 16 mga"
26       }
27     ]
28   },
29   {
30     "optionSet": [
31       {
32         "treatment": [
33           {
34             "requestReference": "MedicationRequest/4399"
35           }
36         ],
37         "explanation": "An interaction has been found between Loperamide_as_needed
38           and recommend_anti_nausea: The metabolism of Ondansetron can be decreased
39           when combined with Loperamide. This option suggests to omit Ondansetron
40           and continue with Loperamide"
41       },
42       {
43         "treatment": [
44           {
45             "requestReference": "MedicationRequest/4379"
46           }
47         ],
48         "explanation": "Loperamide can be started at an initial dose of 4mg followed
49           by 2mg every 2-4 hours or after every unformed stool [II, B]. The maximum
50           daily dose of loperamide is 16 mg.One should pay attention to the risk of
51           causing paralytic ileus and, even if rare, these patients need to be
52           monitored while using high-dose loperamide.After 48 hours, in the absence
53           of efficacy of loperamide, administration of other drugs should be
54           considered."
55       }
56     ]
57   }
58 ]

```